

Cobalt(II) complexes of a benzimidazole functionalized tridented nitrogen-donor imino-pyridine ligand: Synthesis, characterization and phenoxazinone synthase activity studies

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In the present report, a nitrogen-donor benzimidazole functionalized imine based tridentate ligand: 2-(1H-benzo[d]imidazol-2-yl)-N-(1-(pyridin-2-yl)ethylidene)aniline (**HL**) and its cobalt(II) complex (**1**) have been synthesized in good yield. The ligand **HL** is unstable; cyclizes via a C-N bond formation reaction to result a new compound **D**. The cobalt complex **1** has been characterized by using various physicochemical characterization techniques as well as single crystal X-ray structure determination. The electronic structure of the complex **1** was studied by cyclic voltammetry, UV-Vis spectroscopy and DFT calculations. The complex (**1**) is an active catalyst for phenoxazinone synthase activity in methanol medium under aerobic condition. The oxidation of 2-aminophenol (OAPH) to 2-aminophenoxazine-3-one (APX) follows a saturation rate kinetics with the formation of a catalyst-substrate adduct. Mechanism of the reaction was studied by ESI-MS and EPR spectroscopy that showed indeed a catalyst-substrate adduct formation during the reaction. A sharp EPR signal at $g = 2.006$ indicates generation of an organic radical during the oxidation reaction. The catalyst is found to be quite active with a turnover number (K_{cat}) of 52.5 h^{-1} .

Keywords: Imino-pyridine ligand, cobalt(II) complex, single crystal X-ray structure, phenoxazinone synthase activity.

Introduction

Transition metal complexes of tridented ligands have received world wide research attention in recent times¹⁻³. For example, complexes with phosphine donor pincer type tridented ligands have been found to be very stable and active complex for organometallic catalysis^{1,2}. Chirik *et al.*³ and others⁴ have reported a series of transition metal pincer complexes using redox non-innocent bis-iminopyridine as ligand (Scheme 1, **L**₁) those are efficient for catalytic chemical transformations.

Scheme 1. The ligands.

Very recently, Rauchfuss *et al.*⁵ have reported an imino

pyridine based phosphine donor tridented ligand and its iron complex which is very active catalyst for catalytic hydrofunctionalization of alkenes (Scheme 1, **L**₂).

Notably, beyond organometallic catalysis, imine based transition metal complexes are also active in mimicking the activity of biologically active enzymes^{6,7}. For example, a series of copper(II), manganese(II/III), iron(III), and cobalt(II/III) complexes of imine based ligands^{6,7} have been reported that shows phenoxazinone synthase activity, catecholase activity etc. in solution. Here we report a cobalt complex of a benzimidazole functionalized nitrogen-donor new tridented ligand (Scheme 1, **HL**) that acts as an active catalyst for phenoxazinone synthase activity with overall high turnover number.

Experimental

Materials:

All reagents were of analytical grade purity, commercially available and used without further purification. Solvents used were purified and dried by standard procedures. Hydrated

cobalt salt was purchased from the Merck India Pvt. Ltd. Tetrabutylammonium perchlorate was prepared and recrystallized as reported earlier. Caution! Perchlorate salts are potentially explosive, should be handled with care!!

Physical measurements:

Cyclic voltammetry was carried out in 0.1 M Bu₄NClO₄ acetonitrile solutions using a three-electrode configuration (platinum working electrode, Pt counter electrode, Ag/AgCl reference electrode) and a PC controlled PAR model 273A electrochemistry system. A Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer was used to collect microanalytical data (C, H, N). ESI-Mass Spectra were recorded on a Bruker maxis impact spectrometer. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded with 400 MHz JEOL spectrometer. Chemical shifts are reported as δ -values relative to an internal reference of tetramethylsilane (TMS) for ¹H NMR and the solvent peak in the case of ¹³C NMR. IR spectroscopic data were obtained with Bruker Platinum-ATR instrument. UV-Vis spectra and kinetics study were performed on a Cary 8454 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The spectroscopic grade solvents were used for spectroscopic and electrochemical studies. X-band EPR spectra were recorded with a Bruker EMX spectrometer. Room-temperature magnetic moment measurements for complex **1** was performed with Gouy balance (Sherwood Scientific, Cambridge, UK).

Synthesis of ligand (HL):

The ligand HL was prepared according to literature procedure^{8,9}. However as per our observation, the final step of the ligand synthesis i.e. the condensation of 2-acetyl pyridine with the ammine (Supporting information file, Fig. S1) has resulted two products: the desired ligand (HL) as a minor product and its ring cyclized product **D** as major product. Thus we have tried to improve the purity of the ligand as follows: the crude reaction mixture after removing the solvent was dissolved further in dichloromethane and kept for diffusion of pentane in refrigerator for two days. A solid crystalline compound was separated out from the solution which was identified as the compound **D**. The solution phase of the mixture was collected and evaporated under reduced pressure. ¹H NMR shows that it is a mixture of compounds HL and **D** in 3:2 ratio (Supporting information file, Fig. S2). The ligand HL is unstable and transformed continuously to the compound **D**. Thus this mixture was used for complex synthesis immediately.

Synthesis of complex 1:

One equivalent of CoCl₂·6H₂O (57 mg, 0.240 mmol) was dissolved in methanol. Approximately two equivalent of the 3:2 mixture of the ligand (HL):**D** (150 mg, 0.480 mmol) was dissolved in methanol and added to the CoCl₂·6H₂O solution. Immediately, the color of the reaction mixture was changed to reddish brown. The reaction mixture was kept for stirring at 80°C for 2 h. After that it was cooled and solvent was evaporated under the reduced pressure. Then the crude product was extracted with dichloromethane solvent. It was evaporated further under reduced pressure. Finally, the complex **1** was crystallized by slow evaporation of the methanol solution of this crude reaction mixture. Characterization data of the complex **1** are as follows: Yield: 75%; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₀Cl₂N₄OCO: C, 54.32; H, 3.65; N, 12.67. Found: C, 54.02; H, 3.68; N, 12.65; IR (KBr): 3445 cm⁻¹ (N-H stret.), 1591 cm⁻¹ (N-H bending), 1320 cm⁻¹ (C-N stret. py); UV-Vis: λ_{\max} = 290 nm; λ_{\max} = 300 nm; λ'_{\max} = 352 nm.

Crystal structure determination and refinement:

Crystallographic data for the compound **D** and the complex **1** were collected in Table 1. Suitable X-ray quality crystals of **D** were obtained by diffusion of pentane into dichloromethane solution of the crude reaction mixture. The X-ray diffraction quality crystal of the compound **1** were obtained by slow evaporation of the methanol solution of the reaction mixture. All data were collected on Oxford Diffraction Super Nova (Dual, EOS) diffractometer with monochromatic equipped with Mo K α radiation (λ = 0.71073 Å). The data reduction was done with *CrysAlis* PRO and structures were solved by Olex 2¹⁰, with the super flip structure solution program¹¹, using Charge flipping and refined with the SHELXL¹² refinement package using Least-squares minimization. For the compound **D**: A total of 7448 reflections were collected, out of which 3792 were unique (R_{int} = 0.0703), satisfying the $I > 2\sigma(I)$ criterion, and were used in subsequent analysis. For the complex **1**: A total of 5544 reflections were collected, out of which 3322 were unique (R_{int} = 0.0389), satisfying the $I > 2\sigma(I)$ criterion, and were used in subsequent analysis. The structures were solved by employing the SHELXS-97 program package and was refined by full matrix least square based on F2 (SHELXL-97)¹³. All hydrogens atoms were added in calculated positions. Crystallographic data of **D** and **1** are given below in the Table 1.

Table 1. Crystallographic data of the compound (**D**) and complex **1**

Parameters	Compound (D)	Complex 1
Empirical formula	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₂	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ CoN ₄ O
Formula weight	373.43	474.26
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Orthorhombic
Space group	P2 ₁ /n	Pna2 ₁
<i>a</i> (Å)	6.7826(6)	19.9082(12)
<i>b</i> (Å)	14.2422(13)	10.6992(10)
<i>c</i> (Å)	19.2488(15)	9.8826(6)
α (deg)	90.00	90
β (deg)	94.756(8)	90
γ (deg)	90.00	90
Cell volume	1853.0(3)	2105.0(3)
<i>R</i> -factor	7.03	3.89
<i>Z</i>	4	4
<i>T</i> (K)	293(2)	298
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.088	1.089
ρ_{calcd} (g cm ⁻³)	1.339	1.4964
<i>F</i> (000)	788.0	974.9
2 θ range (deg)	3.56 to 52.7	4.1 to 52.74
Data/restraints/ parameters	3792/1/259	3322/0/269
<i>R</i> ₁ , <i>wR</i> ₂ [<i>I</i> ≥ 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	<i>R</i> ₁ = 0.0703, <i>wR</i> ₂ = 0.1744	<i>R</i> ₁ = 0.0389, <i>wR</i> ₂ = 0.0932
<i>R</i> ₁ , <i>wR</i> ₂ (all data)	<i>R</i> ₁ = 0.1076, <i>wR</i> ₂ = 0.2144	<i>R</i> ₁ = 0.0464, <i>wR</i> ₂ = 0.1002
GOF on <i>F</i> ²	1.037	1.068
Largest difference in peak and hole (e Å ⁻³)	0.38/−0.31	0.31/−0.22

Computational details:

All calculations were performed in Gaussian09 (G09) program¹⁴. Full geometry optimization of the ligand (**HL**) as well as the complex **1** were carried out using Density functional theory method at the RB3LYP and UB3LYP level of theory^{15,16}. The 6-31+G basis set for C, H, N and Cl atoms was used. And the LANL2DZ basic set^{17,18} with effective core potential was used for Co-atom. The vibrational frequency calculations were performed to ensure that the optimized geometries represent the local minima and there are only positive Eigen values. GaussSum^{18d} was used to calculate the percentage contribution of metal and ligand of the molecular orbitals.

Result and discussion**Synthesis and characterizations:**

Our research started with the synthesis of ligand **HL** following the literature procedure^{8,9} (Fig. S1). After several trials we were unsuccessful to isolate the pure ligand (**HL**). Careful examination of the ¹H NMR of the crude product shows that it is a mixture of two products: the ligand **HL** as minor and the compound **D** as major products. To improve the purity of the ligand **HL**, we crystallized the crude reaction mixture by dichloromethane-pentane vapor diffusion in refrigerator at 4°C. After two days a solid crystalline compound separated out from the solution. Its characterization by single crystal X-ray structure determination (*cf.* below) shows that the ligand undergoes chemical transformation via a C-N bond formation reaction to form the new compound **D** (Scheme 2). The ligand **HL** is very unstable and undergoes cyclization reaction spontaneously to form the compound '**D**' (Scheme 2). However ¹H NMR analysis of the solution phase of the mixture upon evaporation of the solvent shows that it is also

Scheme 2. Plausible mechanism for the formation of compound **D**.

a mixture of two compounds **HL** and **D** in 3:2 ratio (Figs. S2 and S3). We have used this mixture for the synthesis of the complex **1**. Notably the compound **D** is not reacting with the metal ions to form its complex. It remains as it is after the complexation reaction. Thus only the ligand **HL** results the isolated cobalt complex **1**. As both the compounds **HL** and **D** have same molecular weight, we found only one molecular ion peak in ESI-MS at *m/z* at 313.1 amu (Fig. S4). Though the ligand **HL** is very unstable, its cobalt complex **1** is highly stable. Physicochemical characterization data indeed are in agreement with the formulation of the complex **1** as Co(**HL**)Cl₂. In IR spectroscopy, complex **1** shows a strong absorptions at 3445 cm⁻¹ and 1591 cm⁻¹ which are assigned

for N-H and imine CH=N stretching frequency respectively (Fig. S5)¹⁹.

X-Ray structure:

Suitable single crystals for X-ray diffraction of the compound 'D' were obtained by diffusion of pentane into dichloromethane solution of the crude product mixture of HL and D. X-Ray structure determination shows that one of the imidazole nitrogen indeed undergoes C-N bond formation reaction in the compound 'D'. However, single crystal X-ray structure determination of the complex **1** showed indeed the complex contains the desired ligand HL. ORTEP of the compound 'D' and **1** are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. (a) ORTEP with atom numbering scheme of the compound **D** with 50% probability level. (b). ORTEP with atom numbering scheme of the complex **1** with 50% probability level.

From the analysis of the X-ray structure of the complex **1**, it is found that the ligand coordinates the metal as a tridentate ligand. The geometry of the complex is a distorted trigonal bipyramidal in which two equatorial position are occupied by the pyridine and imidazole nitrogen atom and one of the axial position is occupied by the imine nitrogen atom

Fig. 2. Trigonal bipyramidal view of the coordination sphere of the complex **1**.

(Fig. 2). Other two position i.e. one axial and one equatorial position are occupied by two chloride ligands. Thus, the complex as a whole is five coordinated complex.

The C6-N2 bond length of the ligand HL in the complex **1** is 1.292(5) Å which is characteristic for a isolated CH=N bond length. The Co-N bond lengths are in the range of 2.05–2.15 Å which is also as usual to the complexes coordinated with the unreduced imino pyridine ligands¹⁹. Thus, complex **1** is the cobalt(II) complex coordinated with the neutral tridentate ligand HL. Characteristics bond lengths, and bond angles of the complex **1** are listed in the Table 2.

The complex is three electrons paramagnetic as evident from its room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurement. Thus, it is a high spin cobalt(II) complex with $S=3/2$ electronic configuration which is further supported by DFT calculation as well (*cf.* below).

Cyclic voltammetry and DFT:

To understand the electrochemical behavior of the complex **1**, we have performed cyclic voltammetry experiment in acetonitrile solution. In cyclic voltammetry, complex **1** has showed a reversible cathodic wave at -0.94 (92) V and an irreversible anodic wave at $+1.02$ V (Fig. 3). Exhaustive electrolysis of the complex **1** at -1.1 V has showed that the cathodic wave is associated with one electron transfer process.

Table 2. X-Ray structure and DFT calculated bond lengths and bond angles

Bonds	Bond lengths (in Å)		Angles	Bond angles (in degree)	
	X-Ray	DFT		X-Ray	DFT
Co1-N1	2.058 (3)	2.14	N1-Co1-N2	75.42 (12)	73.80
Co1-N2	2.158 (3)	2.24	N1-Co1-N3	114.85 (14)	129.24
Co1-N3	2.068 (3)	2.14	N2-Co1-N3	80.41 (12)	79.53
C6-N2	1.292 (5)	1.29	C11-Co1-N1	113.61 (11)	111.95
C14-N3	1.331 (5)	1.34	C11-Co1-N2	85.98 (10)	83.89
C14-N4	1.342 (5)	1.38	C11-Co1-N3	123.91 (11)	118.19
C15-N3	1.398 (5)	1.41	C12-Co1-N1	98.59 (10)	94.79
Co1-Cl1	2.29 (13)	2.25	C12-Co1-N2	173.30 (10)	166.75
Co1-Cl2	2.338 (11)	2.37	C12-Co1-N3	99.78 (9)	100.98
C5-C6	1.478 (5)	1.48	C14-N3-Co1	123.81 (3)	122.72
C8-N2	1.415 (5)	1.42	C15-N3-Co1	130.25 (3)	130.38
C16-N4	1.375 (6)	1.39	C11-Co1-Cl2	99.31 (5)	107.06
C11-C14	1.474 (6)	1.46	C11-C14-N3	126.13 (4)	127.56

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of the complex 1.

However our effort to characterize the one electron reduced complex by EPR was unsuccessful due to its high air sensitivity.

To have insight into the electronic structure of the complex 1 a qualitative DFT calculation was performed. The lower energy optimized structure was obtained with $S=3/2$ configuration of the cobalt center. The optimized bond lengths and bond angles are also in well agreement with the experimental observed data (Table 2). Examination of the spin density plot of the complex 1 showed that 2.68 spin is localized on cobalt(II) centre (Fig. 4). Furthermore, examination of the LUMO of the optimized structure showed that it is mainly localized (96%) on the iminopyridine fragment of the ligand (HL) in the complex 1. Thus the reduction of the complex is

Fig. 4. Spin density plot of the complex 1.

assigned for the ligand reduction whereas the oxidation is assigned for $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}/\text{Co}^{\text{III}}$ oxidation. The FMOs of 1 are shown in Figs. S6-S7.

Phenoxazinone synthase activity studies:

Currently, there has been a large interest in catalytic oxidation reaction of organic compounds following nature's principle^{6,7}. A series of cobalt complexes of imine based ligands have been found to be effective for mimicking the enzymatic oxidation reaction^{7b,c,f,h,i}. Thus, we became interested to study the complex 1 towards aerial oxidation of 2-aminophenol (OAPH). It has indeed been found that the complex 1 is an active catalyst for the oxidation of 2-aminophenol to phenoxazinone (Scheme 3). Notably phenoxazinone is

Scheme 3. Oxidation of OAPH to APX chromophore.

an important compound for the synthesis of actinomycin-D that intercalates to DNA and inhibits DNA-dependent RNA synthesis²⁰.

The reaction was carried out by taking catalyst:substrate in 1:100 mole ratio in methanolic solution. Progress of the reaction was further monitored by UV-Vis spectrophotometrically. The color of the solution was gradually changed to deep brown which indicates the formation of 2-aminophenoxazine-3-one (APX). 2-Aminophenoxazine-3-one has an intense absorption at around 427 nm^{7e,j}. Thus, its formation was monitored by the continuous growth of the absorption at 427 nm (Fig. 5). A blank reaction was also carried out without adding catalyst 1 which showed no significant increase in absorbance in the same span of time. Formation of phenoxazinone was further characterized by ESI-MS studies. In ESI-MS, the isolated product showed a molecular ion peak at m/z 213 amu which corresponds to the molecular weight of the phenoxazinone.

Fig. 5. Growth of 2-aminophenoxazine-3-one formation at 427 nm in MeOH upto 2.5 h in the reaction of 2-aminophenol with the catalyst 1 under aerobic condition at 25°C.

Kinetic experiments of the catalytic reaction were performed by UV-Vis spectrophotometrically at 25°C in methanol to evaluate the catalytic efficiency of the complex 1. For this purpose, a fixed concentration of the catalyst (1×10^{-5} M) was used with varying the substrate, OAPH concentration from 1×10^{-3} M to 1×10^{-2} M in 2.5 ml total volume of solution. Concentration of OAPH was chosen such that it follows pseudo-first order kinetics. The experiment was performed during the time span of 3 min for a particular set of complex-substrate mixture at maximum band 427 nm. The plot of initial rate vs concentration of OAPH is given in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Plot of rate vs [substrate] (OAPH) in presence of complex 1 in methanol (inset: Lineweaver-Burk plot).

The saturation curve was found to follow Michaelis-Menten equation for enzyme catalysis^{7c}. On linearization it gives Lineweaver-Burk plot as shown in Fig. 6 (inset). Metrical parameters such as V_{\max} and K_M were found to be 1.45×10^{-7} (Ms^{-1}) and 1.86×10^{-3} (M) respectively. Turn over number, k_{cat} (h^{-1}) of the complex was calculated by dividing v_{\max} with the concentration of catalyst used. It was found to be 52.5 h^{-1} . The high turn-over number indicates that probably the catalyst-substrate adduct is very fast due to vacancy of sixth coordination site in the complex 1. Examination of EPR of the mixture of the catalyst 1 and OAPH in DMF showed a ligand based signal at $g = 2.006$ (Fig. 7). This indeed indicates formation of a organic radicals upon the oxidation of the OAPH and catalyst 1 adduct in air.

Thus based on the above observation, a proposed mechanism is shown in Scheme 4. It is proposed that initially OAPH forms an adduct with 1 which was confirmed by mass

Fig. 7. X-band EPR spectrum of the OAPH in DMF at 100 K immediately after addition of **1**.

spectroscopy at m/z 621 amu (OAPH-1- K^+) as well. Subsequently the bound OAPH undergoes one electron and proton transfer to oxygen generating a radical which is evident by X-band EPR (Fig. 7). Then this radical subsequently loses second electron and proton to result an oxidised benzoiminoquinone^{7f}. This benzoiminoquinone intermediate further via few steps results the 2-aminophenoxazine-3-one by the reaction with un-reacted OAPH remained in the reaction mixture under areal condition (Scheme 4). During this catalytic cycle a reduced molecular oxygen is indeed generated in the form of H_2O_2 which was identified spectrophotometrically (Fig. S8). Thus it shows indeed air is participating in the oxidation reaction of OAPH. However, the complex **1** may catalyse this oxidation reaction either by the reduction of its redox-noninnocent iminopyridine moiety or by Co^{II} - Co^{III} re-

Scheme 4. Plausible mechanism for the oxidation of OAPH to APX chromophore.

dox couple. Detail study of the reaction mechanism is beyond the scope of this report.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we have synthesized a new cobalt complex **1** with a benzimidazole derived tridentate ligand (**HL**). The cobalt complex **1** has fully characterized by physicochemical characterization techniques as well as single crystal X-ray structure determination, cyclic voltammetry and DFT studies. It has been found that the complex **1** is an active catalyst for phenoxazinone synthase activity. Kinetic study, EPR and ESI-MS analysis indicates that the oxidative transformation of 2-aminophenol to phenoxazinone chromophore undergoes through the catalyst-substrate adduct formation followed by oxidation reaction in multiple steps with overall turnover number of $52.5 h^{-1}$.

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Supporting information

Scheme of ligand synthesis, 1H and ^{13}C NMR data, IR spectrum of the complex **1**, ESI-MS of the mixture of **HL** and **D**, DFT calculated FMOs of **1** are submitted in supporting information file (Figs. S1-S8). Crystallographic data for the structure **D** and **1** has been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC No. 1849573 and 1849572 respectively. Copies of this information may be obtained free of charge from the Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK (E-mail: deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>).

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